

INDICATORS OF QUALITY OF LIFE IN PATIENTS WITH SYPHILIS BEFORE AND AFTER TREATMENT

Narzikulov Rustam Mardanovich

Samarkand State Medical University Department of Skin and Venereal Diseases

Abdiev Jaxongir Otabekovich

Samarkand State Medical University 4th year students

Gayratov Murodjon Bobiljonovich

Samarkand State Medical University 4th year students

Annotation: *This article attempts to reveal the main reasons for assessing the quality of life indicators in patients with syphilis in dynamics. To carry out scientific work, the author carried out the object of the study was 250 patients aged 16–67 years (mean age 23.4 ± 3.9 years) with established diagnoses A51 "Early syphilis", A52 "Late syphilis", A53 "Other and unspecified forms of syphilis". The problem in question is still little studied, therefore, requires more thorough research.*

Key words: *Syphilis, quality of life of patients.*

Introduction: Syphilis (outdated: lues from lat. Lues - infection) is a systemic venereal infectious disease affecting the skin, mucous membranes, internal organs, bones, nervous system with a successive change in the stages of the disease, caused by bacteria of the species *Treponema pallidum* (*pallidum treponema*) subspecies *pallidum*, belonging to the genus *Treponema* (*Treponema*) of the order Spirochaetes (*Spirochaetales*). The prognosis of the disease in most cases is favorable. Timely diagnosis and adequate treatment leads to a complete recovery. However, with a long-term chronic course and in cases of infection of the fetus in the womb,

persistent irreversible changes develop, leading to disability.

Aim: To assess the dynamics of the quality of life of patients with syphilis.

Materials and methods: The object of the study was 250 patients aged 16–67 years (mean age 23.4 ± 3.9 years) with established diagnoses A51 "Early syphilis", A52 "Late syphilis", A53 "Other and unspecified forms of syphilis. To assess the quality of life indicators, a validated SF-36 questionnaire was used, using which patients were tested before treatment, 1 month and 3 months after the end of treatment. The study was conducted on the basis of the Orenburg Regional Clinical Dermatovenerological Dispensary. The questionnaire consists of 36 questions grouped into 8 scales. The data obtained were compared with the results of the reference database of population values of the standardized indicators of the questionnaire for residents of the Russian Federation. The calculation of the integral scales of the questionnaire was carried out according to the methodological recommendations developed by the Preference Company.

Results: In patients with primary syphilis, there was a decrease in the level of quality of life with a predominance of influence on the physical component of health (general health scale) before treatment (decrease to 56.8 - by 12.6%) and after 1 month (decrease to 59.8 -8%), and after 3 months - indicators of quality of life became close to the reference values (65). The greatest decrease was noted in the psychological component of health (on the scales of role activity, general health, vital activity, social functioning, emotional state) before the start of treatment for secondary syphilis (decrease to 49.8-17%), latent early (decrease to 55.2 -8% and late (decrease to 52 - by 13.4%) After 1 month, normalization is noted only with latent early syphilis (up to 59.5), after 3 months - there is a tendency to normalize indicators (up to 57) with latent syphilis late, although the average values for the population were not achieved. During the observation period in the secondary form of nosology, the indicators did not reach the reference indicators. The study showed a slight effect of the disease on the quality of life in latent syphilis, unspecified, both before treatment and after 1 and 3 months from the moment observations.

Conclusions: The study showed the heterogeneity of the impact of this disease on the indicators of the quality of life of patients, while there is a dynamics in their change depending on the stage of the disease, which must be taken into account as an important component for a full psycho-social and physical adaptation after treatment.

LITERATURE

1. Hikmatovich I. N., Xolmatovich J. A., Temirovich E. R. Application of Topical Treatment with Pimicralimus for the Treatment of Papulosis Dermatosis //Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 24-28.
2. Hikmatovich I. N., Temirovich E. R., Toxirovich M. T. Effectiveness of Topical Therapy in the Treatment of Genital Herpes //Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 29-33.
3. Hikmatovich I. N., Temirovich E. R., Toxirovich M. T. Local Treatment of Patients with Genital Herpes //Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 19-23.
4. Hikmatovich I. N. Evaluation of the Efficacy of External Therapy in Sick Children with Alergodermatosis //Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 50-54.
5. Hikmatovich I. N., Toxirovich M. T., Xolmatovich J. A. Effectiveness of Sevoran in the Treatment of Papulosis Dermatosis //Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 40-44.
6. Hikmatovich I. N. Evaluation of the Effectiveness of Peporator Kuralimus in the Treatment of Patients with Atopic Dermatitis //Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 45-49.
7. Hikmatovich I. N., Temirovich E. R., Egamberdiyevich M. A. Clinical Evaluation of the Efficacy of Acne Vulgaris Laser Therapy //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 667-669.

8. Hikmatovich I. N., Temirovich E. R., Xolmatovich J. A. HERPIS VIRUSINI MAHALLIY DAVOLASH UCHUN VIFIRONNI QO‘LLASH //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 349-351.

9. Hikmatovich I. N., Temirovich E. R., Muradovich Y. M. O‘SMIRLARDA YUZAKI PYODERMANI DAVOLASHDA TOPIKAL TERAPIYA //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 355-358.

10. Hikmatovich I. N., Temirovich E. R., Xolmatovich J. A. BOLALAR DERMATOZINI DAVOLASHDA MAHALLIY TERAPIYA SAMARALIGINI BAHOLASH //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 352-354.

11. Islamov N. H., Yusupov M. M., Oripov R. A. CHEKLANGAN SKLERODERMANI DAVOLASHNING SAMARALI //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 14. – C. 324-329.

12. Mardonovich N. R. et al. Epidemiological Analysis of Trichofitia Disease in Samarkand Region //Journal of Survey in Fisheries Sciences. – 2023. – T. 10. – №. 1S. – C. 4981-4994.

13. Anvarovich O. R., Ravshanovich K. K. A New View on the Course of Sexually Transmitted Diseases //Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 189-193.

14. Anvarovich O. R., Javlonovna P. A. Takrakor in the Treatment of Itching Dermatitis //Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 184-188.

15. Anvarovich O. R. Management of Sick Children with Adopic Dermatitis //Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 179-183.

16. Oripov R. A. LABORATORY PARAMETERS IN CHILDREN WITH VERIFIED MENINGITIS //Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 7. – С. 162-168.

17. Davlyatovna K. G., Anvarovich O. R., Xikmatovich I. N. UROGENITAL XLAMIDIYADA MIRAMISTINNING SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH //Нововведения Современного Научного Развития в Эпоху Глобализации: Проблемы и Решения. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 53-59.

18. Kurbonalievich A. S. et al. UROGENITAL CHLAMYDIOSIS IS A CAUSE OF STERILITY AND CHRONIC PROSTATITIS IN MEN //Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 306-310.

19. Anvarovich O. R. et al. ETIOPATHOGENESIS AND CLINICAL COURSE SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF NEURODERMITIS DISEASE //Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 276-280.

20. Bakhodirovich T. I. et al. COMBINED IMMUNOTHERAPY IN THE TREATMENT OF CANDIDIASIAN INFECTIONS OF THE URINARY ORGANS //Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 257-263.

21. Tolibov M. M., qizi Buronova F. Z. MAHALLIY OZON TERAPIYASINI QO ‘LLAGAN HOLDA KOMPLEKS DAVOLASH FONIDA YOSH ERKAKLARDA SURUNKALI URETROGEN PROSTATIT (CUP) KECHISHINI O ‘RGANISH //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 417-421.

22. Tolibov M. M., Shodmonova M. A. BOLALARDA ATOPIK DERMATIT (AD) PATOGENEZIDA GENETIK OMILLARNING ROLINI BAHOLASH VA IMMUNOLOGIK PARAMETRLARGA QARAB ANIQLANGAN POLIMORFIZMLARNING PROGNOSTIK AHAMIYATINI ANIQLASH //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 406-410.

23. Tolibov M. M. et al. ATOPIK DERMATITNI DAVOLASHDA LAZER TERAPIYASINING SAMARADORLIGI //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 286-289.

24. Utayev A. J., Tolibov M. M., Axmedova M. M. MANAGEMENT APPROACHES FOR CHRONIC URETHROGENIC PROSTATITIS //Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 151-156.
25. Makhmudovich T. M. ATOPIC DERMATITIS INCIDENT LEVEL, DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA AND PROGNOSTIC IMPORTANCE //JOURNAL OF APPLIED MEDICAL SCIENCES. – 2023. – Т. 6. – №. 4. – С. 158-168.
26. Толибов М. М. СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМ ЭПИДЕМИОЛОГИИ, МИКРОБИОЛОГИИ И ТЕРАПИИ АКНЕ (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ) //SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 14. – С. 215-224.
27. Ilyayevna P. U. et al. DERMATOSCOPIC PAINTING SOME COMMON DERMATOSES //World scientific research journal. – 2023. – Т. 16. – №. 2. – С. 107-120.
28. Ilyayevna P. U. et al. MODERN TRENDS IN TREATMENT SICK MICROSPORIA //World scientific research journal. – 2023. – Т. 16. – №. 2. – С. 98-106.
29. Kholikovich E. S. et al. APPLICATION OF" BETASALIK" OINTMENT IN THE THERAPY OF CHRONIC INFLAMMATORY AND ALLERGIC DERMATOSES //Journal of new century innovations. – 2023. – Т. 31. – №. 3. – С. 56-62.
30. Мансур Т. М., Вохидов Ж. Ж. СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ БОЛЕЗНИ ВИТИЛИГО //SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 14. – С. 234-244.
31. Мансур Т. М., Вохидов Ж. Ж. СОВРЕМЕННОЙ МЕТОДЫ АЛОПЕЦИЯ ДИАГНОСТИКА И ЛЕЧЕНИЕ //SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 14. – С. 225-233.

32. Толибов М. М. и др. ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ К ЛЕЧЕНИЮ ТЯЖЕЛЫХ ОБОЖЖЕННЫХ БОЛЬНЫХ //SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 14. – С. 190-199.

33. Абдуллаев Д. М., Тошев С. У., Толибов М. М. КОМПЛЕКСНЫЙ МЕТОД ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ВУЛЬГАРНЫХ УГРЕЙ //Актуальные аспекты медицинской деятельности. – 2021. – С. 254-256.